

Effects of interviewer continuity on data quality in a panel survey of older respondents

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Abstract

Conventional wisdom suggests that the same interviewers should be assigned to the same respondents in longitudinal surveys to maintain high response rates and contribute to the quality of the data collected, although this may be difficult and more costly from a survey management perspective. For example, if respondents move between waves, travel costs may outweigh the assumed advantage of higher familiarity between interviewers and respondents. Moreover, previous evidence on the impact of interviewer (dis)continuity on panel attrition, but also on data quality, is mixed, suggesting a more complex interplay between interviewer and respondent (characteristics) than usually assumed. This notion raises several open questions, e.g. what are the relevant conditions that influence the strength and direction of interviewer (dis)continuity effects on cooperation in a panel survey? What is the role of respondent (and interviewer) age? Are there patterns that can be generalized across countries in a cross-national setting? And does the interviewing style of interviewers (e.g. their persuasion strategies) influence the effect of interviewer (dis)continuity on data quality?

To answer these questions, we focus on data from the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) with its target population of respondents aged 50 and over. These data are supplemented by information on interviewer characteristics provided by the national survey agencies, as well as interviewer attitudes, behaviours and expectations from an additional interviewer survey conducted during Wave 9 (2021/2022). Based on these data, we analyse the potential impact of interviewer (dis)continuity on panel attrition and data quality (e.g. item non-response), with a particular focus on the older population, and provide practical advice to survey managers on how to direct their efforts.

1. Introduction

Response rates are important because they serve as indicators of data quality and representativeness. In panel surveys, they are even more important as a reduction in sample size (besides concerns about non-response bias) poses a serious threat for longitudinal analyses (Lynn, 2013). The trend of declining response rates in surveys has intensified after COVID-19 in many countries (Krieger et al., 2023). In response to this trend, researchers and statistical organisations have explored various strategies to mitigate it, including the use of multiple data collection modes (De Leeuw & De Heer, 2002) or the implementation of incentives (Singer & Ye, 2013).

In face-to-face surveys, efforts to reduce non-response have included, inter alia, studying the influence of interviewers. Interviewers are crucial for several reasons. They act as a link between survey agencies and respondents (Campanelli & O'Muircheartaigh, 1999), and they play a vital role in maintaining the quality of data by encouraging respondent motivation and providing support when needed (Hope et al., 2022). In longitudinal surveys, the perceived advantage of assigning the same interviewer to sample members in each wave has a significant impact on survey planning and design decisions, and it has been a common approach among survey agencies conducting panel studies to maintain interviewer consistency by assigning the same interviewer to each respondent throughout the life of the panel (Campanelli & O'Muircheartaigh, 1999).

Longitudinal surveys introduce unique challenges when assessing the impact of interviewers on non-response (Vassallo et al., 2015). Previous findings in this area have yielded mixed results. Vassallo et al. (2015) found that interviewer experience, grade, and continuity positively correlate with respondent cooperation. However, the influence of interviewer personality traits remains unclear, with some studies reporting inconsistent findings. Notably, it appears that during the later stages of longitudinal surveys, the current wave interviewer has the most significant impact on non-response rates. Lynn et al. (2014) found that interviewer continuity reduces refusal rates among respondents aged 60 or under, but not among those over 60. Interestingly, the effectiveness of this continuity effect varies depending on the age of the interviewer. For older sample members, changing the interviewer may be beneficial, particularly if it involves transitioning from a younger to an older interviewer. Contrastingly, Campanelli and O’Muircheartaigh (Campanelli & O’Muircheartaigh, 1999) observed no discernible effect of interviewer continuity on non-response. They noted significant variability in the efficacy of an interviewer continuity strategy among refusals, which could not be explained by individual, household, area, or interviewer characteristics.

Our study aims to address several unresolved questions, including: What are the key factors that dictate the extent and direction of interviewer (dis)continuity effects on cooperation within a panel survey? How does the age of both respondents and interviewers impact this dynamic? Can consistent patterns be identified that are applicable across different countries in a cross-national context? Additionally, we want to explore whether the interviewing techniques employed by interviewers (e.g., their persuasion strategies) shape the impact of interviewer (dis)continuity on data quality.

2. Data and methods

This study uses internal data from Waves 8 and 9 from the Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE). SHARE is a cross-nationally harmonised panel survey focusing on people aged 50 and over (Börsch-Supan et al., 2013). Complementing this dataset, we incorporate internal information on interviewer characteristics from the national survey agencies in Germany and Croatia. These include age, gender, education, and experience as a CAPI interviewer as well as with SHARE data.

Based on these data, our aim is to explore the effect of interviewer (dis-)continuity on response propensity in Wave 9. To achieve this, we first descriptively compare interviewer characteristics in Germany and Croatia to shed light on differences that may influence the interaction between interviewers and respondents. In this respect, we calculate response probabilities based on whether interviews were conducted by the same interviewer as in Wave 8 or not and on the experience level of the interviewer. In a second step, we conduct a multivariate logistic regression analysis, using respondent characteristics from Wave 8, which are available for both respondents and nonrespondents, and interviewer characteristics from Waves 8 and 9 to identify relevant factors influencing response probabilities in Wave 9.

3. Results

3.1 Interviewer characteristics and participation patterns in Waves 8 and 9

When analysing interviewer participation in the last two waves in Germany, we found that out of the 186 interviewers who worked on Wave 8, 124 also worked on Wave 9. Additionally, 143 interviewers participated in Wave 9, with only 17 working exclusively on this wave. In total, 203 interviewers worked on at least one of these waves. In Germany, 24% of the interviewers changed between the two waves. Regarding the demographic characteristics of the interviewers, 46% were female and almost 70% were older than 60 years. In addition, about 40% had more than 10 years of experience with Computer-Assisted Personal Interviewing (CAPI).

In contrast to this, the interviewer composition in Croatia showed some significant differences, probably reflecting a different strategy followed by the survey agency. Here, we found that of the 74 interviewers who worked on Wave 8, 42 also worked on Wave 9. In addition, 57 interviewers participated in Wave 9 and only 15 of them worked exclusively on Wave 9. In total, 89 interviewers participated in at least one of the waves. In Croatia, 30% of respondents experienced a change of interviewer. We also found differences regarding

demographic characteristics of the interviewers between countries. From the total of interviewers in Croatia, 88% were female and about one fourth of them were over 60 years or older. About half of them had between 3 and 10 years of experience as a CAPI interviewer.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of interviewers

	Germany	Croatia
Gender		
Female	46%	88%
Male	54%	12%
Age		
24 - 40 years	2%	35%
41 – 59 years	29%	39%
≥ 60 years	69%	26%
CAPI experience		
≤ 2 years	19%	29%
3-10 years	38%	53%
> 10 years	43%	18%

Source: SHARE Waves 8 and 9, internal data.

3.2 Response probabilities based on interviewer continuity and experience

Table 2 shows retention rates for Germany and Croatia, revealing some differences between the countries. In Germany, retention rates from Wave 8 to Wave 9 were higher when the same interviewer was assigned to both waves. This continuity seems to have a positive effect on the respondents' likelihood to participate again. Conversely, we observed significant lower retention rates when there was a change of interviewer. This suggests that interviewer continuity plays an important role in maintaining respondent engagement and participation in longitudinal surveys.

In Croatia, we observed a different trend. Retention rates from Wave 8 to Wave 9 do not differ much between respondents for which the interviewer stayed the same and those who experienced a change of the interviewer – at least if their experience was the same or higher than before. However, new interviewers with less experience showed much lower retention rates. Thus, unlike in Germany, where the importance of keeping the same interviewer was evident, in Croatia we found that the specific characteristics of the interviewer play a more important role in determining their impact on retention rates.

Table 2. Interviewer classification and effect on retention rates

	Germany				Croatia			
	Retention rate	n	Retention rate	N	Retention rate	n	Retention rate	N
Same interviewer: low experience	83.3	48	86.9	2654	93.3	120	93.1	1331
Same interviewer: medium experience	84.3	606			92.0	538		
Same interviewer: high experience	88.9	1440			94.2	449		
Same interviewer: higher experience	86.0	551			93.3	224		
Different interviewer, same experience: low	100.0	16	70.1	541	94.6	37	94.0	334
Different interviewer, same experience: medium	75.4	61			94.4	107		
Different interviewer, same experience: high	58.9	146			95.5	66		
Different interviewer, higher experience	72.6	318			92.7	124		
Different interviewer, lower experience	80.7	161	80.7	161	75.2	125	75.2	125

Source: SHARE Waves 8 and 9, internal data.

3.3 Effects of interviewer and respondent characteristics on response probability

We examined several factors associated with response probabilities in Wave 9 of the survey. We found that in Germany, respondents who were interviewed by a different interviewer were significantly less likely to participate in the survey than those who had the same interviewer (see Figure 1). In addition, certain respondent characteristics were found to influence the likelihood of responding. Respondents with a migrant background and those who rated their health as poor were correlated with a lower likelihood of responding. In terms of interaction during the survey, respondents who asked for clarification at Wave 8 were less likely to respond in subsequent waves. Furthermore, respondents with high education and those who participated already before Wave 8 showed a higher likelihood of responding in Wave 9.

Figure 1. Average marginal effects of interviewer and respondent characteristics on response probability in Germany

In Croatia, lower response probabilities were observed for respondents assigned to a different interviewer with less CAPI experience and older interviewers aged 50 and over (see Figure 2). In addition, respondents with a higher education, poor health and who had great difficulties in making ends meet also showed lower response probabilities. The same held for households that were more difficult to contact, and respondents who asked for clarification during the survey process in Wave 8. On the other hand, interviewers with a higher level of education and panel respondents who had previously participated in the survey were more likely to respond. Interestingly, there was no significant difference in response probability between younger and older respondents when assigned to the same interviewer. However, interviewer experience played a crucial role in influencing response probabilities, especially for younger respondents between 50 and 64 years (not shown here).

Figure 2. Average marginal effects of interviewer and respondent characteristics on response probability in Croatia

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, our study sheds light on the complex dynamics of interviewer effects in panel surveys, highlighting the existence of notable differences between countries and emphasising the importance of taking contextual factors into account. Contrary to conventional wisdom, our findings suggest that simply using the same interviewer in a panel survey does not inherently guarantee higher participation rates. Rather, the effectiveness of interviewer continuity depends on the experience level of the interviewer in question. While in Germany a positive effect of interviewer continuity could be found, in Croatia, there was a (negative) impact of interviewer continuity on survey response rates if the new interviewer has a lower level of experience than the previous interviewer. These results have to be seen against the background of different hiring and operational strategies that the survey agencies seem to follow: While in Croatia the large majority of interviewers were female and rather young, German interviewers were, on average, more than 60 years old and equally female and male. While we believe that these differences can be attributed for some of the differences we found with regard to survey participation, it is interesting to note that the interaction with experience seems to work in the same direction.

Furthermore, and in line with previous studies (Lynn et al., 2014), our analyses show that the influence of interviewer effects is not uniform across respondents. Instead, it is partly influenced by the educational level of the respondent and their previous experiences with the survey. This highlights the importance of taking respondent characteristics into account when assessing the impact of interviewer continuity on survey participation. Our study also shows the crucial role of interviewer experience in shaping respondent cooperation, particularly in engaging younger respondents. We found that more experienced interviewers were more effective in persuading respondents to participate in surveys, especially among younger people who may face time constraints when participating in face-to-face surveys such as SHARE. By recognising these complexities and tailoring survey strategies accordingly, researchers and survey practitioners can increase the effectiveness of panel surveys and improve data quality. In the future, it is important to continue to investigate the interplay between interviewer characteristics, respondent demographics, and survey outcomes to develop best practices in survey methodology.

5. Next steps

While our results revealed differences between the two samples in Germany and Croatia, pointing to a more complex interplay between interviewer and respondent characteristics, integrating information from the SHARE interviewer survey, particularly on interviewer persuasion, attitudes, and expectations, could further enrich our understanding of the mechanisms underlying interviewer effects on non-response. By looking more closely at interviewer characteristics and behaviours, we can identify strategies to improve survey participation and data quality. In addition, given the disparities observed, we plan to extend our analysis to other countries. This will allow us to better understand country-specific factors influencing survey participation and data quality.

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Bibliography

- Börsch-Supan, A., Brandt, M., Hunkler, C., Kneip, T., Korbmayer, J., Malter, F., Schaan, B., Stuck, S., & Zuber, S. (2013). Data Resource Profile: The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 42(4), 992–1001.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyt088>
- Campanelli, P., & O’Muircheartaigh, C. (1999). Interviewers, Interviewer Continuity, and Panel Survey Nonresponse. *Quality and Quantity*, 33(1), 59–76. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004357711258>
- De Leeuw, E., & De Heer, W. (2002). Trends in household survey nonresponse: A longitudinal and international comparison. In R. Groves & Z. Batagelj, *Survey Nonresponse* (pp. 41–54). Wiley.
- Hope, S., Campanelli, P., Nicolaas, G., Lynn, P., & Jäckle, A. (2022). The Role of the Interviewer in Producing Mode Effects: Results From a Mixed Modes Experiment Comparing Face-to-Face, Telephone and Web Administration. *Survey Research Methods*, 207-226 Pages.
<https://doi.org/10.18148/SRM/2022.V16I2.7771>

- Krieger, N., LeBlanc, M., Waterman, P. D., Reisner, S. L., Testa, C., & Chen, J. T. (2023). Decreasing Survey Response Rates in the Time of COVID-19: Implications for Analyses of Population Health and Health Inequities. *American Journal of Public Health, 113*(6), 667–670.
<https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2023.307267>
- Lynn, P. (2013). Alternative Sequential Mixed-Mode Designs: Effects on Attrition Rates, Attrition Bias, and Costs. *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology, 1*(2), 183–205.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jssam/smt015>
- Lynn, P., Kaminska, O., & Goldstein, H. (2014). Panel Attrition: How Important is Interviewer Continuity? *Journal of Official Statistics, 30*(3), 443–457. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jos-2014-0028>
- Singer, E., & Ye, C. (2013). The Use and Effects of Incentives in Surveys. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science, 645*, 112–141. JSTOR.
- Vassallo, R., Durrant, G. B., Smith, P. W. F., & Goldstein, H. (2015). Interviewer Effects on Non-Response Propensity in Longitudinal Surveys: A Multilevel Modelling Approach. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series A: Statistics in Society, 178*(1), 83–99.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/rssa.12049>